

D1.1 Website and social media accounts and power-point template

WP1 Coordination

Responsible Partner: WP1

Contributing partners: ANSES, UoS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D1.1 name of the deliverable
WP and Task	WP1; Task 1.4
Leader	ANSES/UoS
Other contributors	Sciensano
Due month of the deliverable	M6
Actual submission month	M8
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	DEC
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Table of contents

I ONE HEALTH EJP WEBSITE	4
II ONE HEALTH EJP SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS	5
ANNEX 1 WEBSITE SCREENSHOTS	6
ANNEX 2 SOCIAL MEDIA SCENSHOTS	12
ANNEX 3 TEMPLATES SCREENSHOT	14
ANNEX 4 SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE STATISTICS 2016	20
ANNEX 5 WEBSITE GUIDELINES	21

ONE HEALTH EJP WEBSITE

The main tool supporting communication activities including the dissemination of the results is the One Health EJP website. The website is online and accessible via <http://onehealthejp.eu/> and is built and managed by UoS staff.

The website is addressed to the general public, professionals and policy makers, provides information on the project, updates on progress and results. The aim of this website is to highlight the objectives of the project and includes the most important outputs (methodologies, results, presentations, reports) as soon as they are produced. The website establishes an open channel with stakeholders asking for suggestions and feedback.

The website is work in progress, and it is in continual development for the duration of the project. The portal has innovative aspects, such as web 2.0 tools, such as links to social networks, links to an internal and external newsletter, and we are currently looking at the feasibility and options of including a video conferencing platform for communication across the EJP platform.

Considering the objectives, the web portal is developed in two phases, the first and current phase is descriptive, and the second considers the results and the materials produced.

To provide continuity and accessibility to the materials and results produced, we are investigating possible strategies to sustain the website for at least two years after the end of the project. However, the funding and platform for this is still yet to be established.

The contents of the website aim to illustrate the entire process and the actions of the One Health EJP especially:

- Aims and objectives: A summarized overview of the background, vision, aims and objectives and the sustainability of the EJP project.
- Consortium: The 40 consortium partners are listed on the website, and will feature an interactive geolocation map showing all institute locations. When the user clicks on one of the location pins, this will link to the institute's own dedicated web page. Information on this page includes a short abstract describing the institute, any links to the institute website or social media pages, contact details of the institute representative and scientific representative at the institute, the institute logo and finally a corporate photograph.
- Research and Integrative Projects: An explanation of how the joint research projects and joint integrative projects contribute fit in the EJP project. Each JRP and JIP has its own dedicated page with an abstract and photograph.
- Structure: The One Health EJP work plan is structured in seven work packages, each targeted towards specific overarching needs and objectives, as well as ensuring alignment and integration in the implementation of the programme. A visual representation of the structure of the One Health EJP is given and the respective work packages are briefly described.

The website also includes a private area used to support internal communication and facilitate project management across the EJP consortium. Each EJP member can create their own user login account, which gives access to the private area. In this private area, EJP members can create different 'groups'. These groups can gather and share resources, deliverables, milestones, tasks, and products useful for

all the partners. The deliverables and milestones can be automatically mapped into each user's calendar. The privacy and administrative settings on each group can be tailored to suit the user needs. The EJP consortium members can communicate with other consortium members either through group discussion forums or private messaging functionality.

The Communications Task Force, consisting of the Communications officer supported by the Coordination members, has created a list of secondary tasks, which is constantly being updated with ideas for additional website features. This will be implemented over the course of the project.

II ONE HEALTH EJP SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

The Web strategy also provides ongoing activity on social networks. Social media activity contributes to achieve the external communication's objectives by:

- Actively involving stakeholders and public
- Collecting information
- Promoting behavioural changes

Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have been created. The choice of these social networks is motivated by their high popularity in Europe.

Visiting social media websites and participating in online social networks are common online activities. An average of 38 percent of individuals in the European Union used social networks daily in 2016 (Annex 4). The penetration rate is higher among individuals who use the internet regularly. It is likely that in the future this will increase further, given the widespread use of smartphones and tablets which make it even easier to connect throughout the day.

ANNEX 1 WEBSITE SCREENSHOTS

I/ Public pages

a) Homepage

b) About page

About

Vision

This programme will create a research community across Europe with food, medical, veterinary and environmental health scientists working together. Such an interdisciplinary and international approach is essential to address the threats of zoonotic disease and antimicrobial resistance.

Background

This landmark partnership between 38 acclaimed food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and, the Med-Vet-Net-Association (MVNA) is an exemplar of the 'One Health' concept.

The One Health concept recognizes that the human health is tightly connected to the health of animals and the environment. Animal feed, human food, animal and human health and environmental contamination are all closely linked. The study of infectious agents that may cross these barriers is the main focus of the new One Health European Joint Programme (EJP), which is a novel H2020 scheme supported by the EU.

Within a network of 38 laboratories and research centres across 19 member states, there are representatives from food, medical, veterinary and environmental health research. These centres represent a solid framework for an integrated research community and aim to achieve significant advances in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. Consistent with the "Prevent-Detect-Respond" concept, the One Health EJP aims at reinforcing collaboration between institutes by enhancing transdisciplinary cooperation and integration of activities by means of dedicated Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects and through education and training activities. The programme includes alignment and harmonization with on-going EC-funded research projects, and deliverables from the One Health EJP will feed into evidence based risk assessment for national authorities.

Management and sustainability

The One Health EJP also aims to develop sustainable programmes and projects beyond its five year lifespan, through the production of a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (2021-2030) and a European P2P One Health Cooperative Joint Initiative.

The network is managed by the constitution of three bodies: a Programme Managers Committee (PMC), a Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and the EJP Project Management Team (EJP-PMT), supported by a Support Team (ST) for the daily follow-up of the science and a Support Team for the daily follow-up of administrative financial and legal matters. The French agency for food, environmental and occupational health & safety (ANSES) is coordinator. The EJP consortium will be interacting with the relevant ministries in each partner state, and is overseen by an External Scientific Advisory Board and a Stakeholder Committee.

“Based on the MedVetNet network of excellence (FP6) and the MedVetNet Association, this OneHealth EJP is a promising network of mainly reference laboratories for infectious disease in humans and animals aiming to integrate and align work processes of joint priority and through joint research.”

-French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)

c) Consortium page

The screenshot shows the Consortium page of the ne HEALTH EJP website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'Consortium', 'Projects', 'Structure', and 'Main Contacts'. Below the menu is a map of Europe with red location pins indicating the presence of consortium members in various countries including Ireland, France, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Turkey, and others. Below the map, there is a grid of logos for the member agencies, each with a 'Pinpoint' icon below it:

- Animal & Plant Health Agency
- AGES (Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety)
- BFSA (Bulgarian Food Safety Agency)
- Cantacuzino
- DTU Food (National Food Institute)
- anses (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety)
- INRA (Science & Impact)
- FLI (Frederich-Loeffler-Institut)

d) Projects page (to be updated later on)

Research and Integrative Projects

The ambition of the One Health EJP is to align European countries through **joint priority setting** in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, and **joint programming of research agendas**.

Our approach is to set up a common strategic research agenda among the partners, taking into account the initiatives taken by EFSA, ECDC and the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE). Also, through the existing links with the Programme Owners (national/regional authorities and policy makers) national interests are taken account of in the EJP strategy.

There is considerable opportunity for **harmonization of approaches, methodologies, databases and procedures** for the assessment and management of food-borne hazards, emerging threats and AMR across Europe, which will improve the quality and compatibility of information for decision making.

e) Structure page (to be updated later on)

Structure

The One Health EJP work plan is structured in **seven work packages**, each targeted towards specific overarching needs and objectives, as well as ensuring alignment and integration in the implementation of the programme. A visual representation of the structure of the One Health EJP is given in the figure below and the respective work packages (WP) are described.

f) Main Contacts page

About Consortium Projects ▾ Structure Main Contacts

Main Contacts

--	---	--	--

II/ Private pages

a) User profile

ACTIVITY PROFILE NOTIFICATIONS MESSAGES FRIENDS GROUPS FORUMS ARTICLES SETTINGS

VIEW **EDIT** CHANGE PROFILE PHOTO CHANGE COVER IMAGE

EDITING 'BASE' PROFILE GROUP

Name (required)

This field can be seen by: Everyone

b) Groups

Search Groups...

ALL GROUPS 29 MY GROUPS 8 CREATE A GROUP

ORDER BY: LAST ACTIVE

<p>WP4 2</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 4 2 hours ago</p> <p>WP4</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP LEAVE GROUP</p>	<p>WP1 5</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 1 4 hours ago</p> <p>WP1</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP LEAVE GROUP</p>	<p>CT 3</p> <p>Coordination Team a day ago</p> <p>Coordination Team</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP LEAVE GROUP</p>	<p>EJP Consortium Members a day ago</p> <p>Find all key project documents and milestones in this group.</p> <p>PUBLIC GROUP LEAVE GROUP</p>
--	--	--	--

c) Tasks

My Tasks

Overview
 Activity
 Current Task
 Outstanding Task
 Completed Task

1 0 0

At a glance

Current	1 Task
Outstanding	0 Tasks
Completed	0 Tasks

Activity

Activity Assigned Completed July 2018

Date	Activity	Assigned	Completed
Jul 09	0	0	0
Jul 10	1000	0	0
Jul 12	0	0	0

d) Calendar

Calendar

-Select Project Filter

< > today

July 2018

month week day

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28

ANNEX 2 SOCIAL MEDIA SCreenshots

One Health EJP Twitter account: @OneHealthEJP

This screenshot shows the top portion of the OneHealthEJP Twitter profile. The header features navigation icons for Home, Moments, Notifications, and Messages, along with a search bar and a 'Tweet' button. The main banner area contains the 'Horizon 2020' logo and a text box stating: 'Creating a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary & food institutes through joint programming of research agendas matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.' Below the banner, the profile statistics are listed: 3 Tweets, 28 Following, 55 Followers, 2 Likes, 0 Lists, and 0 Moments. The 'Who to follow' section on the right lists John Legere (@JohnLeg...), One Health NUG (@onehe...), and Eelco Franz (@EelcoFranz).

This screenshot displays the main feed of the OneHealthEJP Twitter account. The top banner is identical to the previous screenshot. The feed shows three tweets. The first tweet, dated Jun 7, includes a photo of a presentation slide titled 'One Health NUG' and a group of people on a stage. The second tweet, dated May 18, features a photo of a group of people standing together. The third tweet, dated May 24, shows a photo of a 'COHESIVE kick off' event. The right sidebar contains the 'Who to follow' list and 'Trends for you' section, which includes hashtags like #WorldCupRussia2018 and #GreenForGreenfall.

One Health EJP LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2020-one-health-ejp/>

ANNEX 3 TEMPLATES SCREENSHOT

Minutes of the meeting template:

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773630.

<div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <p>Logo of the hosting</p> </div>	<h2 style="margin: 0;">Minutes</h2> <p style="font-size: 1.2em; margin: 5px 0;">One Health EJP</p> <p style="font-weight: bold; margin: 5px 0;">Grant Agreement number 773830</p>
--	---

Date	
Venue	
Meeting	
Room	

Meeting Minutes

Discussed topics

Example:

- 1- Administratives points
- 2- Financial points
- 3- Scientific and technical point

Deadlines / Action plan:

Actions and decisions	Responsible Partner	Deadline

List of documents attached to the minutes:

-
-

Add your logo (host)

One Health EJP
 XXXX meeting hosted by (organisation acronym) in (town), (country)
 (dates)

Attendance list template:

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830.

[logo of the hosting institution]	Attendance List One Health EJP Grant Agreement number 773830	
-----------------------------------	---	---

Date	
Venue	
Meeting	

Organisation	Participants	Arrival Time	Departure Time	Signature
ASSOCIATED PARTNERS				
01 – ANSES				
02 – AGES				
03 – CODA-CERVA				
04 – WIV-ISP-IPH				
05 - NCIPD				
06 – NDVRI - BFSa				

Add your logo (host)

One Health EJP

XXXX meeting hosted by (organisation acronym) in (town), (country)

(dates)

Agenda template:

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Logo of the host institution	<h2 style="margin: 0;">Agenda</h2> <p style="margin: 0;">One Health EJP</p> <p style="margin: 0;">Grant Agreement number 773830</p>
------------------------------	--

Date	
Venue	
Meeting	
Room	

Meeting agenda

00:00-00:00 **XXXX MEETING Day 1: (date)**

00:00-00:00 **Subjects, Responsible**

00:00-00:00 **Coffee break**

00:00-00:00 **Subjects, Responsible**

00:00-00:30 **XXXX MEETING Day 2: (date)**

00:00-00:00 **Subjects, Responsible**

Logo of host institution *[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]*
[date]

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

00:00-00:00 **Lunch**

00:00-00:00 **Subjects, Responsible**

Decisions to be adopted during the XXXX meeting

Decision	Support document	Management Body	Vote Requirements

Logo of host institution *[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]*
[date]

Internal meeting invitation

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

<div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 80%; height: 80%; margin: auto;"> <p>Logo of the host institution</p> </div>	<h2>Meeting invitation</h2> <h3>One Health EJP</h3> <p>Grant Agreement number 773830</p>
--	--

Name of the meeting	
Logistics	
Date	
Venue	
Time	<i>Please mention here if round trip day is feasible or if overnight is preferable</i>
Organising institution	
Organiser & event contact person	
Room	
Teleconference	Yes/no
Videoconference	Yes/no
Content	
Purpose	
Attendees	<i>Please mention here the number and to whom the invitation has been sent out (e.g. scientific representatives)</i>
WP(s) involved	
Related JRPs/JIPs	
Relevant documents	
Budget	
Budget reference out of which the related costs must be charged by your Institute	<i>Please contact the Support Team if needed</i>

Logo of host institution [name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]
[date]

Deliverable template:

DX.X Name of the deliverable

WPX Name of the WP

Responsible Partner: XXX
Contributing partners: XXX

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	DX.X name of the deliverable
WP and Task	WPX; Task X.X
Leader	XXX
Other contributors	XXX
Due month of the deliverable	MX
Actual submission month	MX
Type R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc. OTHER	X
Dissemination level PU: Public CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	X

Meeting template for WP leader:

The slide features the ne HEALTHEJP logo at the top left. The main title is "Name of the meeting" in a large blue font. Below it, three lines of placeholder text are shown in orange: "[name of the WP]", "[name of the WP leader]", and "[name of the institution]". Further down, the text "Organisation, Location" and "Date" is displayed in a smaller grey font. In the bottom left corner, it says "Logo of the hosting institution". In the bottom right corner, there is a small European Union flag and a line of fine print: "This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830."

Meeting template for project leader:

The slide features the ne HEALTHEJP logo at the top left. The main title is "Name of the meeting" in a large blue font. Below it, three lines of placeholder text are shown in orange: "[name of the project]", "[name of the project leader]", and "[name of the institution]". Further down, the text "Organisation, Location" and "Date" is displayed in a smaller grey font. In the bottom left corner, it says "Logo of the hosting institution". In the bottom right corner, there is a small European Union flag and a line of fine print: "This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830."

ANNEX 4 SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE STATISTICS 2016

ANNEX 5 WEBSITE GUIDELINES

ONE HEALTH
EUROPEAN JOINT PROGRAMME

WEBSITE GUIDELINES

MEMBERS AREA USER MANUAL

Contents

Contents.....	2
About.....	3
Key Information	4
Contact Us.....	4
Browser.....	4
Your Profile.....	5
Groups	9
Roles and Responsibilities.....	9
To invite users to a group.....	11
To accept an invitation to a group.....	12
Discussion Forums (within groups).....	13
Document Store (within groups).....	14
Members.....	15
Activity.....	16
Viewing my Tasks in a list	17
Viewing my tasks on my calendar	18
PART 1: EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones	20
EJP-defined deliverables.....	20
EJP-defined milestones	21
PART 2: My Own Deliverables and Milestones	22
My own Tasks (high level).....	22
My own Deliverables	23
My own Tasks (low-level) and Sub Tasks (under deliverables).....	24
My Own Milestones.....	27
Annex 1: Preset Groups setup by CTF.....	28

About

The One Health EJP website has a public interface but also boasts a private space. Only members of the EJP consortium can register to use the private space of the website to create their own account. This private space works on the basis of creating groups. We encourage members to create groups as required using these guidelines. Members can create public (all members) or restricted groups (selected members), upload and share documents and create discussion forums. Members can track their EJP-defined deliverables and milestones (D&M) consistent with the EJP Grant Agreement (G.A.) if they belong to a work package (WP), joint integrative project or joint research project. Members can also add their own tasks under these EJP- defined D&M, and also add their own personal D&M. All D&M of the groups that members belong to can be viewed in members' task lists or on their personal calendar. This document is intended to help members to navigate and use the private space features, and to facilitate communication and collaboration across the consortium.

Key Information

Website location: <https://onehealthjp.eu>

Contact Us

If you have any issues with the website, or would like to provide some useful feedback, please use the 'Contact Us' form by clicking on the icon indicated. Alternatively, you can contact the Communications Task Force (CTF).

COMMUNICATIONS TASK FORCE

Name	Role	Email
Piyali Basu	Communications Officer	p.basu@surrey.ac.uk
Fanny Baudoin	CTF member	Fanny.Baudoin@sciensano.be
Camille Pestre	CTF member	camille.pestre@anses.fr

Browser

If you use the website on Internet Explorer, please be aware not all of the features are supported by this browser. We recommend using Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox browsers.

Your Profile

Purpose

Your profile is a hub of your activity within the One Health EJP website. You'll find all requests for 'Friendship' and Groups listed here.

Registration

1. Go to <https://onehealthjep.eu> and click Register in the top navigation menu
2. Ensure ALL fields in your profile are complete to make sure you are identifiable. **You MUST use your institute email ID (not a personal email address) to be identifiable.** If you are not identifiable, the CTF will first try contact you to complete your profile, however if your profile is not completed, the CTF has the right to reject your request.

Create an Account

Registering for this site is easy. Just fill in the fields below, and we'll get a new account set up for you in no time.

Account Details

Username (required)

Email Address (required)

Choose a Password (required)

Confirm Password (required)

Profile Details

Full Name (required)

Institute name (required)

Affiliated activity (required)

Country (required)

Role in the EJP (required)

Complete Sign Up

3. Once the CTF accepts the request, the activation link will be sent to your registered email address.

WARNING: The email is sent from "WordPress" and may be sent directly into your junk mail.

Mon 02/01/2018 16:22

One Health EJP <wordpress@onehealthjep.eu>

[One Health EJP] Activate your account

To

One Health EJP

Hi

Thanks for registering!

To complete the activation of your account, go to the following link:

<https://onehealthjep.eu/activate/SyA5pH295kIByc20cF74cRrYD4G3EAMC/>

© 2018 One Health EJP

[unsubscribe](#)

4. Click the link in your email or copy and paste it into your browser
5. Click 'Activate' to activate your account

ne HEALTHEJP European Commission

About Consortium Research Projects Structure Main Contacts

Activate Your Account

Please provide a valid activation key.

Activation Key:

Activate

6. Click 'Log in' to log into your new account.

ne HEALTHEJP European Commission

About Consortium Research Projects Structure Main Contacts

Account Activated

Your account is now active!

Your account was activated successfully! You can now [log in](#) with the username and password you provided when you signed up.

7. You will be redirected to your profile page.

Navigate to your main Profile

1. To navigate to your profile, hover over the top right-hand corner of your screen. Here you can find your new notifications and messages.
2. Click your username to visit your profile

Update your main Profile

1. To update your profile, click on *Profile > Edit*
2. Ensure ALL fields in your profile are complete. The fields required are Full Name, Institute, Country, Affiliated activity and Role in EJP and these need to all be completed to make sure you are identifiable and you have access to all the relevant resources.
3. Click *Save* to update your profile

Customise your profile

1. Click the 'Profile' icon

2. Here you can upload a profile image and a cover image (the background to your profile)

Groups

Purpose

All project management happens under groups. Groups can be created by any website member, and the creator will automatically be a group admin (see below for further information) and members can be invited to that group. The access rights are defined by the group admin (see roles and responsibilities).

At the start of the website creation, the CTF already created some 'preset groups' (see Annex 1, and the EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones associated with these preset groups).

Roles and Responsibilities

Members of a group can have different access level rights.

Role of group admins

Highest level of authority.

Only the leaders and the deputy leaders (if applicable) of the WPs, Research Projects and Integrative Project can be group admins.

Can promote or demote the status of members according to access requirements

Can edit or delete the group itself

Comment on existing deliverables or milestones

Permission to mark EJP-defined deliverables and milestones as complete

Send invites

Accept membership request

Create discussion forum

Upload and share documents

Permission to upload deliverable into *finalised deliverables* folder

Role of group moderators

One level down from Admins

Can perform all admin actions as group admins can, but they cannot edit or delete the group.

Able to upload and share documents

Role of group users

Standard group user

Can only view and download documents. Cannot upload and share documents

Can only view or comment on existing deliverables or milestones

Create discussion forum

- EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones have already been entered for all WP and projects. See PART1: EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones section for complete information.
- These **MUST NOT be changed** under any circumstances.
- If you encounter any **delays**, you can leave a comment by selecting the speech bubble.
- If you find any inconsistencies, please contact the CTF (see Contact Us)
- For every deliverable two “tasks” were added:
 - **A reminder** two weeks before the deadline
 - **Deadline** of the deliverable on the day

Only the preset group admins have permission to mark these deliverables and milestones as complete (see EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones)

To create a group

1. Navigate to Groups in the top navigation
2. Click *Create a Group*
3. Fill in all necessary details. Here you can specify whether

Groups Members Activity My Calendar My Tasks Logout

About Consortium Projects Structure Main Contacts

Groups Home / Groups / Create a Group

1. Details 2. Settings 3. Forum 4. Photo 5. Documents 6. Cover Image 7. Invites

Group Name (required)

Group Description (required)

Create Group and Continue

To invite users to a group

Important reminder: Admins should only invite members who are a part of the EJP consortium and are working on the activity of the group. Group admins can also review pending requests to join the group on the **Manage > Members** page or on your notifications (see My Profile)

1. Visit your selected group
2. Click *'SEND INVITES'*

Navigation bar with icons: HOME, FORUM, DOCUMENTS (0), MEMBERS (7), **SEND INVITES** (highlighted with a red box), TASKS, MANAGE.

User profile: **travistest**
active 1 minute ago

Send Invites (highlighted with a red box)

To accept an invitation to a group

<p>WP5 ¹</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 5 8 days ago</p> <p>WP5</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP <input type="button" value="REQUEST MEMBERSHIP"/></p>	<p>WP4 ¹</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 4 8 days ago</p> <p>WP4</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP <input type="button" value="REQUEST MEMBERSHIP"/></p>	<p>WP7 ¹</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 7 8 days ago</p> <p>WP7</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP <input type="button" value="REQUEST MEMBERSHIP"/></p>	<p>WP6 ¹</p> <p>WORK PACKAGE 6 8 days ago</p> <p>WP6</p> <p>PRIVATE GROUP <input checked="" type="button" value="ACCEPT INVITATION"/></p>
--	--	--	--

Discussion Forums (within groups)

Purpose

You can create a post in the group forum that will be posted for all group members to see and comment on.

Key points

- These posts are only public to members of your group
- Any group members can subscribe to your forum.
- Posts can be created within discussion forums
- Users can be tagged using *@examplename* in posts

Document Store (within groups)

Purpose

Documents can be added for viewing and download within groups. A selection of documents relevant to each preset group (see EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones) have already been uploaded.

Key points

- Documents up to 1GB can be uploaded
- Allowed file formats - odt, ods, rtf, txt, doc, docx, xls, xlsx, ppt, pps, pptx, ppsx, pdf, jpg, jpeg, gif, png, zip, tar, gz
- Only group members can access these documents. **Important reminder: The sensitivity and confidentiality of documents should be considered when uploading documents into the group. Please seek to gain permission from the relevant lead person if necessary.**
- Categories can be created when uploading the document which makes it easier to search through the group documents.

Members

Groups **Members** Activity My Calendar My Tasks Logout

About Consortium **Projects** Structure Main Contacts

Search Members...

Advanced Search Hide/Show Form

First Name

Surname

Institute name

WP1
WP2
WP3
WP4

Role in the EJP

Search

Purpose

The members' area allows you to search for colleagues site-wide.

To search for members:

1. Click on *Members*
2. Under Advanced Search, click on *Hide/show form*
3. Fill in known fields
4. Click *Search*

Activity

Purpose

The activity page displays all the actions (like deliverables creation, task creation, completion etc) in a chronological manner and date wise. The items are clickable to view more information on the recent activity.

Viewing my Tasks in a list

Purpose

Check day to day, weekly or monthly progress of your Tasks on your Tasks list.

Note: To add your tasks to your calendar, please see [Tasks and Subtasks \(below\)](#).

Viewing my tasks on my calendar

The screenshot shows the 'My Calendar' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'My Calendar' highlighted in a red box. Below the navigation bar, there is a header with the 'ne HEALTHEJP' logo and the European Union flag. The main content area is titled 'Calendar' and features a filter dropdown set to '-Select Project' and a 'Filter' button. The calendar is displayed in a monthly view for July 2018, with tabs for 'month', 'week', and 'day'. The calendar grid shows tasks and milestones for each day, including 'IMPART Submit D-1.A.', 'Fanny - enter all project D&M in website', 'Task #1', 'AIR SAMPLE Reminder D-JRP3', 'AIR SAMPLE Submit D-JRP9-2', '07.3 Deadline', '07.4 Deadline', '07.4 Deadline Reminder', 'Fanny - Draft the website pages for the projects', 'Fanny - prepare Newsletter with CTF', and 'Fanny - Rename all the project tasks'. Milestones are highlighted in blue, and tasks are highlighted in green.

Purpose

Check day to day, weekly or monthly progress of your Tasks on the calendar. You can even drag and drop items to change due dates. Deliverables and milestones can be distinguished by their colors. You can choose which group tasks you want to appear by selecting the corresponding group in the filter (scroll down menu up left).

You can also view your tasks on your personal calendar by going to My Tasks > scroll down to My Calendar.

Note: To add items to your calendar, please see Tasks and Subtasks (below).

My Tasks

Overview
 Activity
 Current Task
 Outstanding Task
 Completed Task

Piyali

My Calendar

 August 2018
 month week day

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
29	30	31	1	2	3	4

PART 1: EJP-defined Deliverables and Milestones

It is important to understand the nomenclature and hierarchical structure of High-level Tasks, Deliverables, Milestones, Low-level tasks and Sub Tasks to use the website to its full capacity.

[High-level Tasks](#) > [Deliverables](#) > [Low-level Tasks](#) > [Sub Tasks](#)

[High-level Tasks](#) > [Milestones](#)

In the EJP G.A., there are 'Tasks', under which the EJP deliverables and milestones have been defined. To keep it consistent, the levels on the website have been named to be consistent with the G.A.

Groups for all WP, current Research Projects, Integrative Projects and EJP teams have been created. These groups will be collectively referred to as **"Preset groups"** from this point onwards.

EJP-defined deliverables

[High-level Tasks](#) > [Deliverables](#) > [Low-level Tasks](#) > [Sub Tasks](#)

Within the group (e.g. ARDIG), click on "Tasks", then within "Deliverables" click on Tasks. By selecting the little square next to the task, the admin marks the task as done. This will notify us that you are aware you have a deliverable to submit (= reminder) and later that it was indeed submitted. (=Deadline)

The deliverable report can be uploaded into the group files *Finalised deliverables*.

EJP-defined milestones

High-level Tasks > Milestones

The milestones can be accessed by the group admins by selecting Milestones. The group admin can mark a milestone as complete by selecting the little check mark.

PART 2: My Own Deliverables and Milestones

However, members are free to create their personal deliverables and milestones under their own high level Tasks. To be clear, these are NOT official deliverables to be submitted to the REA. Please be aware these are visible to others in the group. However, it will not appear in other members' calendars unless the low-level task is specifically assigned to a member.

My own Tasks (high level)

In this context, the High-level tasks can be thought of as projects, under which you have your own deliverables and/or milestones. Low-level tasks can be added to break the deliverables into smaller low-level tasks. These low-level tasks can be further broken down into sub-tasks to monitor smaller activities.

[High-level Tasks](#) > Deliverables > Low-level Tasks > Sub Tasks

[High-level Tasks](#) > Milestones

WORK PACKAGE 6

Home / Groups / WORK PACKAGE 6

 WP6

Private Group
an hour ago

GROUP ADMINS

Horizon 2020
Creating a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary & food institutes through joint programming of research agendas matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.

LEAVE GROUP

HOME FORUM DOCUMENTS (7) MEMBERS (2) SEND INVITES **TASKS** MANAGE

Purpose

High-level tasks can be defined as different projects under one group.

To add a new high level Task:

1. Go to your group, and click on *Tasks*
2. Here, you can view an overview summary of your main Tasks. Click on *New Task*
3. Fill in the required fields

My own Deliverables

High-level Tasks > Deliverables > Low-level Tasks > Sub Tasks

The screenshot shows the 'Deliverables and Milestones WPS' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for HOME, FORUM, DOCUMENTS (7), MEMBERS (2), SEND INVITES, TASKS, and MANAGE. Below this is a header for 'Deliverables and Milestones WPS' with an 'Edit' button and a settings icon. A horizontal menu contains 'Overview' (280), 'Activities' (0), 'Discussions' (0), 'Deliverables' (22), 'Milestones' (19), 'Files' (7), and 'Settings'. The 'Deliverables' tab is highlighted with a red box. Below the menu is a blue button labeled 'New Deliverable' with a plus icon, also highlighted with a red box. The main content area shows a calendar for 'July 12 2018 - July 12 2018' with a 'New Task' button, a '0 Completed' status, '1 Incomplete' status, and '0 Comments'. A progress bar at the bottom right indicates 0% completion.

To add a new Deliverable:

1. Go to your Task in the group
2. Click on *New Deliverable*
3. Fill in the required fields

4. Under this deliverable, Click on *New Task*
5. Fill in required fields
6. **To add a due date for this deliverable, a new task needs to be created (see tasks and subtasks)**

My own Tasks (low-level) and Sub Tasks (under deliverables)

Purpose

Tasks should be related to a Deliverable. A Sub Task is a second level of items within an existing task. Sub Task can be assigned to yourself or your teammates/co-workers. Instead of creating too many Tasks, you can create fewer Tasks with much broader titles and add Sub Tasks underneath.

Key points

- Tasks that have dates and assigned users assigned to them are visible on the Calendar.

- Sub Tasks do not show up on the Calendar - only under 'My Tasks'
- Reminder emails are sent only for Tasks with dates and assigned users

To create your own low level Tasks and Sub Tasks

1. Find the specific deliverable you will be working on then click *New Task* to create a new Task under that deliverable
2. Once a new task has been created, open the task window pane to see, comment on and complete Sub Tasks
3. Add a due date to your task by clicking on the calendar icon and enter the start date and end date

Example: Due date of 18th July 2018 would have this date as the start date and the end date. You will receive email notifications for each day in the range you specify.

WARNING: After specifying your start date and end date, you must click out of the calendar and then PRESS REFRESH in order to update the deadline correctly. If you do not press refresh, the deadline will not be updated.

4. For this to appear on a member's calendar, the task needs to be assigned to a specific user

5. Complete Tasks by clicking on the box next to the task
6. To create a subtask, click *New sub task* in the task window pane under the Task description
7. Alternatively click on the circled plus sign on your deliverable summary next to your task title to create a new sub task

8. Complete Sub Tasks by clicking the box next to the sub task in the task window pane

WARNING: If you do not assign a task a user it will not show up on the calendar

Watch an instructional video

Video link: <https://applaud.fleeq.io/l/gribzedbxi-pbs8zfj8gx?ap=1>

My Own Milestones

High-level Tasks > Milestones

Purpose

Milestones can also be created and represent key points in the Deliverables lifecycle.

Key points

- Milestones that have due dates and users assigned to them are automatically visible on the Calendar.
- Reminder emails are automatically sent for Milestones

To add a new milestone:

1. Go to your Task in the group
2. Click on *Add Milestone*
3. Fill in the required fields
4. This can be automatically viewed in your personal calendar (see Viewing my tasks on my calendar)

Annex 1: Preset Groups setup by CTF

1. EJP Consortium Members (Public Group)
2. Programme Management Team
3. Coordination Team
4. Programme Owner Committee
5. External Scientific Advisory Board
6. Communication Contact Persons
7. Communication Task Force
8. Stakeholders
9. Finance Team
10. Work Package 1
11. Work Package 2
12. Work Package 3
13. Work Package 4
14. Work Package 5
15. Work Package 6
16. Work Package 7
17. ORION (Joint Integrative Project)
18. RaDAR (Joint Research Project)
19. COHESIVE (Joint Integrative Project)
20. Tox-Detect (Joint Research Project)
21. MoMIR-PPC (Joint Research Project)
22. LISTAdapt (Joint Research Project)
23. MedVetKlebs (Joint Research Project)
24. NOVA (Joint Research Project)
25. MAD-VIR (Joint Research Project)
26. ARDIG (Joint Research Project)
27. AIR SAMPLE (Joint Research Project)
28. IMPART (Joint Research Project)
29. METASTAVA (Joint Research Project)